

File Carving Techniques Using Scalpel

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Abstract-File carving is an important technique in digital forensics. File carvers can retrieve files from raw disk by using database of headers and footers. Scalpel is one of the best forensics tool in Kali Linux. Scalpel was created as an improvement of Foremost 0.69. Earlier versions of Foremost have some issue when it gets some heavy CPU jobs, Scalpel overcomes it. Scalpel can easily recover permanently deleted data. This paper presents the step-by-step process of implementation and file carving using Scalpel.

I.INTRODUCTION

Scalpel is an open-source file recovery tool which is compatible with Linux and Windows. The first version of Scalpel was based on Foremost 0.69, which is released in 2005. Scalpel has the following additional features including;

- minimum carve sizes can be specified, which helps to narrow down the search and perform faster.
- Performs faster on multicore CPUs by multithreaded execution.
- asynchronous I/O operation permits other operations to overlap with pattern matching, which results in a substantial performance improvement.
- provision to specify regular expressions for header and footer.
- embedded header/footer matching for better processing of structured file types that may contain embedded files.

Scalpel comes with a configuration file with multiple standardized options to perform the recovery. All the standard configurations will be present in this file as commented, User can uncomment the required configurations to perform recovery. It mainly carves the file based on the file types. E.g PDF, JPG etc. Scalpel also has the option to perform recovery using header and footer patterns. These patterns will be either in fixed binary strings or regular expressions. You must modify the configuration file according to the requirement, before running scalpel to activate it. Scalpel options are detailed in the Scalpel man page. Scalpel can execute in Windows without any command

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line arguments using a precompiled version of Scalpel. But in Unix and Mac OS, compilation is necessary.

II.LITERATURE SURVEY

As Golden G. Richard III and Vassil Roussev have said in their paper file carving is an important digital forensics technique and its applicability is beyond the digital investigation Many file carving applications are available but none(except scalpel) of them are able to quickly perform file carving operations with limited number of resources. Scalpel is an improved version of foremost 0.69. It also shares some of the code with foremost. But it comes with an optimized carving strategy to avoid unnecessary memory-to-memory copies and disk I/O. To complete user defined carving operations, scalpel should perform at most 2 sequential passes over an image file. Scalpel also performs much faster on Pentium class hardware with least configurations of RAM and no swap

III.METHODOLOGY

Steps for recovering files using scalpel:

- Edit scalpel configuration file uncommenting all the file formats we want to recover.
- Specify the device to carve files.
- Specify the directory where scalpel will place the recovered files.

Screenshots

1. Scalpel configuration file.

2. Uncommenting file types.

- To find partition of the system fdisk-l is used.

- The following command is given to start carving of lost files. Scalpel -o root/Desktop/recovered/ /dev/sdb1

IV.RESULT

After the recovery, all the deleted files will be displayed in the output directory that we mentioned in the recovery process. An audit.txt file and the recovered files are stored in separate folders according to their types are displayed in this output directory. The audit.txt files containing the information of the recovered files.

V.CONCLUSION

File carving is an important digital forensics technique. Many file carving applications are currently available, but none are able to quickly perform file carving operations. Scalpel is an open source file carving tool. Which is an improved version of Foremost 0.69. Scalpel has a significantly optimized carving strategy, which avoids unnecessary memory-to-memory copies and disk I/O. Scalpel performs at most 2 sequential passes over an image file to complete a set of user defined carving operations and exhibits excellent performance on Pentium class hardware with less amounts of RAM and no swap.

VI.FUTURE WORK

Several things giving greater value to scalpel are currently underway. One is more accurate header observations, in the polished and tasteful form of the UNIX text record need. This has need of some care, because over-zealous looking into details of text record forms and sizes may outcome in design in wood operations not being done when the wrong text record

facts (perhaps because of, in relation to an toover-written solid mass, for example) may be only slightly damaged and in fact, usable. We are also making into company scalpels text record design in wood techniques into our frame-work for made distribution by numbers, electronic forensic, to rate of motion design in wood operations on very greatly sized images. It may be possible to rate of motion up the windows account of scalpel further this is is currently an open question under discussion . At last, we need to make high-level language into machine language and test scalpel on other UNIX flat structures, covering mac OS X. In the future, we hope that working together with persons making observations working on coming-stage by numbers, electronic forensics expert ways, such as made automatic reassembly of broken down documents which are beyond the powers of the current

living-stage of general text record persons, things making cuts, will give in even more powerful text record design in wood applications .

VII.REFERENCES

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